

India's Digital Transformation by Optimized Payment Solution – A Bird's Eye View

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Abstract

Digital India the flagship innovative program has transformed the Indian banking and financial system by introducing digitalization to the door step of each citizen. Rupay, the national equivalent of credit and debit cards of Visa, Mastercard etc., has been assimilated into banking eco-system where the cost to market and customer is reduced for each transaction. UPI and BHIM enables mobile payments using QR codes and mobile numbers linked to Aadhar, the national identity number enables banking transactions to be easy, fast, secure and safe as the interface is national with no interventions from outside agencies like SWIFT. FinTech, as it is called has spearheaded a revolution on financial inclusion, optimization, bandwidth connectivity, technological gadgets integrated into both bank's networks and financial tech companies for seamless transactions from all media including net banking, mobile, QR, customer account to merchant account etc., Digital payment has made fund transfer both receiving and payments as simple as we could understand in the context of holding the power to enhance monetary value to our activities.

RuPay, as it stands empowers Indian banking system for its standalone service and recent effort to integrate with south Asian countries like Bhutan, Singapore and few European countries for international transactions.

Optimising our customer focused digital systems needs concerted effort in improving bandwidth, internet connectivity, penetration of mobile phones, digital literacy, ability to utilize technological expertise of IT skilled experts and government support to install and implement advanced versions of the payment systems for digital economy to grow.

Digital India

'There is an explosion of Fintech innovation and enterprise in India. It has turned India into a leading Fintech and Start-up nation in the world, the future of Fintech and Industry 4.0 is emerging in India', ¹ Narendra Modi, Prime Minister of India. Digital India is a government flagship program with the vision to digitalize economy and empower people for faceless, paperless and cashless transactions. Motto of digital India launched in 2015 is 'power to empower' the knowledge economy. Digital India vision is to improve digital infrastructure, governance of digital systems and give revolutionary power to citizens with access to commerce, law, health, banking, trade, government channels etc., and having impact on millions of Indians. RBI's 'Payments Vision 2025' 'E-Payments for Everyone, Everywhere, Every-time' (4Es) ² with the aim to provide users with safe, secure, fast, convenient, accessible and affordable e-payment options is realized.

Digital India has its mission to offer high speed internet to all Gram Panchayats, online e-seva centres, connecting high speed internet to all government agencies, villages, taluks and remote areas for e-governance, introduce digital literacy and transform digitally empowered nation by transparent governance enabled with Aadhar (Digital ID Program), BharatNet, fibre optic networks and Wi-Fi hotspots.

Digitalization

Digitalization helps agricultural economy using internet, mobile data, analytics, AI, digital services & apps including AgriTech as valuable national asset thereby preparing the nation for future as knowledge economy.

Government of India enables digitalized financial economy to promote inclusion. Boosting digital payments systems like QR for small and medium enterprises in urban, semi-urban and rural areas, focus is on technology, to transform government agencies, business houses, corporates, households, vendors and collective economy on tech enabled e-platforms.

Rupay

Rupay is the Indian multinational financial payment services launched by NPCI on 26th March 2012. National Payments Corporation of India (NPCI) under Section 25 of Companies Act, 1956 and Section 8 of Companies Act 2013, the umbrella organization initiated technology based banking infrastructure to provide secure electronic payment system as part of Payment and Settlement Act, 2007 powered by RBI and Indian Bank's Association. It is served to PSU banks via Jan Dhan Scheme of Central Government. ³

Rupay is Indian payment network designed for domestic use as debit, credit cards (classic, Platinum, Select) charging less fees for each cashless data processing and verification done by Indian processors and increased market share as more than 1000 tech savvy banks issued 600 million Rupay

cards offering safe and secured transactions. Further, Rupay contactless has vision of one card for all payments to revolutionize wallet based, in-store merchant specific apps.

As payment gateway, Rupay's objective is financial inclusion, wherein the domestic card payment network enables multiple and loop based financial instruments for an economical fee and no processing fee for Indian consumers.

Digital Payments

Digital payments are electronic by using digital devices like mobiles, computers, point of sale, merchandising gadgets, wireless channels to transfer funds from one account to another. India uses digital payment apps like BHIM, UPI, GooglePe, PhonePe, Paytm, Amazon Pay and others. It includes verification and authentication of each transaction. Digital and mobile payment is done through e-wallets, in-apps, wireless, bank debit & credit cards & account numbers, bills, virtual cards, ACH, electronic checks, merchant accounts, mobile wallets, contactless, internet banking, e-commerce and online, NFC and QR codes under separate protocol. It can be Person to Person (P2P), Person to bank account (P2A), person to merchant (P2M) and transactions through Aadhar linked mobile, bank accounts with IFSC Code for real time interbank electronic fund transfer (NEFT/MICR/SWIFT) under Immediate Payment Service (IMPS) System.⁴ Digital payments impact small business, street vendors and migrant workers for fast bank to bank, bank to merchant transactions in small amounts.

Features

Digital payment system offers advantages like speed, convenience, storage, globalized platforms, low cost, multiple transactional choice, easy installation and usage, manageable protocols and interfaces like UPI. India has increased the ecosystem in the past 5 years installing secure, reliable, scalable, acceptable, flexible, convertible, efficient, ease of use applications for e-payment and has pioneered in usage of QR codes.

India's Digital Payment Eco-System

Indians use cards, online payment platforms and Rupay for flexible, omni-banking vendor applications supporting their customers to transform to digital platforms. Wallets has gained new users in India and are popular payment methods than cards for online shopping and transactions. India promotes digital payments by linking Aadhar and mobile numbers to facilitate Public Financial Management System (PFMS) in Panchayats, ration shops and Tahsildar offices. India's Payment strategy is to conduct industrial and business research on mobile /digital payment economy. It identifies latest technological trends and models to

adapt to Indian digital ecosystem which is volume and agile.

Fintech

Financial Stability Board (FSB) defines FinTech as 'technology-enabled innovation in financial services that could result in new business models, applications, processes or products with an associated material effect on the provision of financial services'.⁵ ABCD of Fintech includes AI, Block Chain, Cloud Computing and Big Data utilized by banks, financial institutions, mobile banking, automated portfolio managers for real time currency payments, Insur-Tech, Robo advisory services, alternative lending systems etc.,⁶ Fintech industry integrates major functions of banks and financial institutions to enhance service quality and provide multiple services on unified platform to retain customer base and increase market share.

Digital payment, a key FinTech solution is growing to deliver instant payments, reception, online and ecommerce payments, Agri-Tech, e-Kranti seva, digitalized big data and mobile banking using cloud etc., with technological intervention. NPCI as a Fintech company introduced Unified Payment Interface (UPI) to facilitate inter-back peer to peer (P2P) and person to merchant (P2M) transactions wherein two mobile devices play role in transferring funds instantly.

NFC: Near Field Communication (NFC) payment enables android powered smartphones, where users tap, pay and make through installed in-app payments. It is a way of processing payments for contactless credit card transactions by Rupay.⁷

UPI: UPI is India's real time payment system and Rupay is NPCI's proprietary card payment solution on nation-wide UPI infrastructure. It is a central utility and does not depend on single institution. It is a dynamic infrastructure based on secure IMPS system to establish digital payment gateway. Cost of UPI is shared by government subsidies and cost to market UPI is user friendly interface with wide range of features. UPI as digital transaction reduces costs and risks of handling cash, improve transparency and increase ease of online payments. Digital services enable automation, connectivity, communication, speedy transactions, information, storage, e-work force on multiple interfaces on one application.

UPI is an alternative to SWIFT and operates 25 apps according to India Digital Payment Report by Worldline. NPCI deploys Rupay and UPI outside of India in Singapore, UAE, Malaysia, France, Belgium, Netherlands, Luxembourg and Switzerland. Bhutan accepts UPI enabled BHIM app transactions.⁸ UPI technology enables more than 200 million transactions every day over 280 banks linked to it and SBI is the leading banker with more than 130 crore of UPI transactions. UPI-

BHIM as government enabled secure, reliable cashless payment system, is widely accepted digital payment system. It enables users to link multiple bank accounts, mobile numbers using In-built apps.

Bhim

BHIM (Bharat Interface for Money) is managed and developed by NPCI (National Payment Corporation of India) to enable retail payment systems in India. It is an inter-connection between UPI applications and bank accounts. BHIM transaction can be done using a VPA (Virtual Payment Address – UPI ID) without a bank account or IFSC code.⁹

BHIM uses three levels of authentication, app to phone, app to bank and bank to phone. It also uses UPI to transfer funds from account to account. Is safe as it uses finger print authentication or PIN making it safe and reliable as secure mode of money transfer for users through mobile platform using UPI.

Optimization

Optimization involves storage capacity of payment gateways. Systems and solutions integrate bank account numbers, transaction history, nodes of different players like SWIFT / MICR/ IFSC, banks own payment gateways / retail payment solution providers like Rupay Concept of optimization achieves efficiency given the criteria that the payment system integrates multiple nodes to connect peer to peer, peer to mobile, mobile to bank etc., where instant real time transaction is enabled.

Optimization for multiple transactions on national gateways reduces transaction costs and risks for better returns to the owners of gateway systems like NPCI and BHIM. Optimization of the powerful payment gateway systems manages its infrastructure, POS, client- systems like applications, e-commerce solutions to interconnect banks, merchants, UPI, Rupay, BHIM interfaces entire payment channel to maximize transaction value. Solving optimization problems is by improving the speed of network, seamless transactions between multiple owners of transactional interface and the payment gateway (BHIM) as a mobile app.

Challenges To Optimized Payment Solutions

Digital divide like illiteracy, bottlenecks in infrastructure, internet speed, data theft, cyber-attack, access restrictions mis-coordination amongst various departments, less penetration of e-governance, mobile phones online tax payment etc., has to be overcome. India being a digital economy, is inevitable to deploy robust, reliable and secure payment gateway for digital transactions. To transform into a digital eco-system needs to revitalize its legacy payment solutions and shorten digital skill gap among work force, reduce risks of

hacking and theft to promote risk averse business culture.

Indian government shall increase its budget to install technological infrastructure and transform payments and reception of funds on secure and safe digital platforms, bandwidth, multiple currency handling, data security, technical infrastructure, user knowledge and experienced personnel to manage electronic and mobile payment systems.

Conclusion

Global innovation Index ranks India in 40th position and 5th largest economy according to Digital Economy Report 2022, where digital divide can be reduced by affordable bandwidth, internet connection, electronic devices, digital technologies, technical expertise and proper IT education.¹⁰ A national digital plan mounted on digital technology and IT expertise is necessary for India's digital transformation to adopt programs and platforms on digital resources for rapid development.

NPCI require significant talent to grow from low cost value added service provider to high value service provider and capacity to serve demands of burgeoning digital economy of India.¹¹ Providing secure data connection for transactions, compliance to financial laws & regulation to secure transactions against fraud and theft, improve technological expertise and digital skill sets to ensure user experience is essential.

Digital payment revolutionizes mobile payments used for recharge, online bills, orders etc., It enables Indians banks and financial institutions to install innovative and collaborative infrastructure to modernize IT framework & systems to enhance operational excellence. The main difference is its operating costs. Digital payment systems need integrity, authorization, confidentiality, availability and reliability. Only with authorization, a user /merchant can deduct funds from account. Fintech companies improve digital payment systems, develop innovative solutions by removing barriers in implementing real time applications. Optimization of a financial ecosystem needs research on IT processes and software to build apps, infrastructure to communicate, store and transmit data for faster and accurate transactions within the context of national payment systems.

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